

The modified Bessel K functions and the Fourier Transform of q-Gaussians

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Torino, December 7, 2023

Abstract –Here we show that the Fourier transform of the q-exponential Tsallis functions (also known as q-Gaussians) are generating time correlation functions based on the modified Bessel functions of the second kind. For the q parameter ranging from 2 to 1, we pass from a correlation which is an exponential decaying with time (Laplace distribution) to a Gaussian-like behavior.

Keywords: q-Gaussian Tsallis lines, Time correlation functions, WolframAlpha software

The q-Gaussians, also known as "Tsallis functions", are probability distributions derived from the Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Hanel et al., 2009). The q-Gaussians are based on a generalized form of the exponential function (see discussion in Sparavigna, 2022), characterized by a continuous parameter q in the range $1 < q < 3$. As given by Umarov et al., 2008, the q-Gaussian is based on function $f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2)$, where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a constant. The q-exponential has expression: $exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$. The function $f(x)$ possesses a bell-shaped profile, and, in the case that we have the peak at position x_o , the q-Gaussian is given as:

$$\text{q-Gaussian} = C \exp_q(-\beta(x - x_o)^2) = C [1 - (1 - q)\beta(x - x_o)^2]^{1/(1-q)} \quad (1)$$

Here we will consider (1) in the following form, with dimensionless variable w about $w_o = 0$:

$$\text{q-Gaussian} = C \exp_q(-w^2) = C [1 - (1 - q)w^2]^{1/(1-q)} \quad (2)$$

For q equal to 2, the q-Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009). For q close to 1, the q-Gaussian is a Gaussian. Consequently, for the q-parameter between 1 and 2, the shape of the q-Gaussian function is intermediate between the Gaussian and the Lorentzian profiles. Due to this feature, the q-Gaussians turn out to be suitable for being used as line shape in the Raman spectroscopy (see Sparavigna, 2023; for instance [ChemRxiv1](#), [ChemRxiv2](#), [ChemRxiv3](#), [ChemRxiv4](#), [SSRN](#)). In [Ze nodo](#), in discussing the time correlation functions related to Raman line profiles, we started using the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussians. Let us remember that the Fourier transform of a Lorentzian lineshape is producing a time correlation function which is an exponential decaying with time (Laplace distribution). In the case of the Gaussian lineshape, we have a correlation with is a Gaussian function of time. Being the q-Gaussian a lineshape which is intermediate between Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles, the related time correlation function must be intermediate between exponential and Gaussian functions.

Rodrigues and Giraldo, 2015, have considered in detail the Fourier transform of the q-Gaussian functions. Here we use a more phenomenological approach. Let us start from the link between the q-Gaussians and the Bessel functions.

In [Wikipedia](#) it is told that the "Bessel functions can be described as Fourier transforms of powers of quadratic functions". Function K_ν is a modified Bessel function of the second kind, order ν . For instance:

$$2 K_0(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i\omega t}}{\sqrt{t^2 + 1}} dt.$$

To have further cases, we can use the on-line Fourier transform calculator, at <https://www.wolframalpha.com>. Following the notation in Wikipedia, we can find, for instance:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 + (At)^2)^{-1/2} e^{i\omega t} dt = \frac{1}{\sqrt{A^2}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \cdot K_0\left(\frac{|\omega|}{\sqrt{A^2}}\right)$$

Note that, in this example, we can see evidenced the time/frequency scaling.

Here, in the following, let us consider some cases of Fourier transform (WolframAlpha) with exponent $-1/(q-1)$, that is $1/(1-q)$ as in (2). The Fourier transform is from the frequency domain w to the time domain t (dimensionless variables):

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(q-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{q-1}\right)} \cdot 2^{\frac{q-2}{q-1}} \cdot |t|^{\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{1}{2}} \cdot K_{\frac{1}{q-1} - \frac{1}{2}}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

Posing $\xi = 1/(q-1)$:

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-\xi}](t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\xi)} \cdot 2^{(q-2)\xi} \cdot |t|^{\xi - \frac{1}{2}} \cdot K_{\xi - \frac{1}{2}}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

To illustrate the behavior of the Fourier transform, let us consider different values of q , starting from $q=3$, including $q=2$ (Lorentzian), to find the corresponding time correlations (see [Zenodo](#) for discussion about time correlation in Raman spectroscopy). From WolframAlpha, we have:

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(3-1)}](t) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} K_0(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

By the way, the q -Gaussian is defined for q ranging from 1 to 3.

Fourier transform in the case $q=3$

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(2.5-1)}](t) = 0.930437 \cdot |t|^{0.166667} \cdot K_{0.166667}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))$$

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(2-1)}](t) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} e^{-|t|} \quad (\text{a})$$

(Fourier transform of the Lorentzian function). In (a) we can find the Laplace distribution.

$$F_w[(1 + w^2)^{-1/(1.9999-1)}](t) = 0.999988 \cdot |t|^{0.5001} \cdot K_{0.5001}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t)) \quad (\text{a'})$$

We can deduce that the exponential is equal to a K Bessel function multiplied by a square root, so that:

$$K_{0.5}(t \operatorname{sgn}(t)) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{|t|}} e^{-|t|}.$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.9-1)}](t) = 0.977728 \cdot |t|^{0.611111} \cdot K_{0.611111}(t \operatorname{sgn} t) \quad (b)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.7-1)}](t) = 0.838525 \cdot |t|^{0.928571} \cdot K_{0.928571}(t \operatorname{sgn} t) \quad (c)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.5-1)}](t) = \frac{0.626657}{t^2} \cdot e^{-|t|} \cdot |t|^2 \cdot (|t|+1) = 0.626657 \cdot e^{-|t|} \cdot (|t|+1) \quad (d)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.4999-1)}](t) = 0.499777 \cdot |t|^{1.5} \cdot K_{1.5}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

We have, as given by WolframAlpha, that: $K_{1.5}(t) = \frac{1.253314137}{\sqrt{t}} \cdot e^{-t} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{t} + 1\right)$, and therefore (d).

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.4-1)}](t) = 0.265962 \cdot |t|^2 \cdot K_2(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.3-1)}](t) = 0.0714233 \cdot |t|^{2.83333} \cdot K_{2.83333}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

$$F_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.15-1)}](t) = 0.000050 \cdot |t|^{6.16667} \cdot K_{6.16667}(t \operatorname{sgn} t)$$

Fourier transforms of four cases given above.

Let us add some further screenshots.

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.25-1)}](t) = \frac{1}{t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4} |t|^{3.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \\ (0.0261107 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.156664 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.391661 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.391661)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.2-1)}](t) = \\ \frac{1}{t^5 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^5} |t|^{4.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} (0.00326384 t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4 + \\ 0.0326384 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.146873 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.342703 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.342703)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_w[(1+w^2)^{-1/(1.125-1)}](t) = \\ \frac{1}{t^8 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^8} |t|^{7.5} e^{-t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} \sqrt{t \operatorname{sgn}(t)} (1.94276 \times 10^{-6} t^7 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^7 + \\ 0.0000543973 t^6 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^6 + 0.000734364 t^5 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^5 + 0.0061197 t^4 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^4 + \\ 0.0336583 t^3 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^3 + 0.12117 t^2 \operatorname{sgn}(t)^2 + 0.262535 t \operatorname{sgn}(t) + 0.262535)$$

Using the results given above and considering the scaling $(q-1)w^2$ into $t/\sqrt{(q-1)}$, we can plot some time correlations as in the Figure 1 and Figure 2 (semi logarithmic scale).

Figure 1: Fourier transforms of some q -Gaussians as given by WolframAlpha, for some values of the q parameter.

Figure 2: The same as in the Figure 1, in semi-logarithmic scale. For $q=2$, we have a correlation which is an exponential function (straight red line). For q closer to 1, the curve is Gaussian-like (parabolic behavior in the semi-log plot).

In Wikipedia, https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Distribuzione_di_Laplace, we can find mentioned the Sargan distributions, given in the following form:

$$f_p(x) = \frac{1}{2} \exp(-\alpha|x|) \frac{1 + \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j \alpha^j |x|^j}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^p j! \beta_j}.$$

In the screenshots and in (d), we can find suggested the Sargan distributions indeed. As told by Kotz and coworkers (2001), "For $\lambda = r + 1/2$, where r is a non-negative integer, the Bessel function K_λ has the closed form":

$$K_{r+1/2}(u) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2u}} e^{-u} \sum_{k=0}^r \frac{(r+k)!}{(r-k)!k!} (2u)^{-k} \quad (*)$$

This is formula A.0.10 in Kotz et al., 2001. For $r = 0$, we have (A.0.11):

$$K_{1/2}(u) = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2u}} e^{-u}.$$

(see also the discussion at 4.4.3 in Kotz et al., 2001).

Let us consider again: $K_{1.5}(t) = \frac{1.253314137}{\sqrt{t}} \cdot e^{(-t)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{t} + 1\right)$. It is easy to find that this expression agrees with (*).

Remarks

Some might say that the q-Gaussian function, also known as "Tsallis function", is a form of the t-Student distribution. Moyano et al., 2006, are indicating that the q-Gaussian "recovers the t-Student distribution with l degrees of freedom if $q = (3 + l)/(l + 1)$. For $l = 1$, hence $q = 2$, we get the Cauchy-Lorentz distribution". Let us evaluate q as a function of the degrees of freedom (integer values).

Using integers for the degree-of-freedom, the q-parameter has discrete values.

The q-Gaussian is not the t-Student function since we have a different parametrization. If we imagine building a fitting approach of Raman spectra based on t-Student, we have parameter values ranging from 1 to infinity, From the point of view of the numerical approach, the use of a parameter in the range from 1 to 2, or even from 1 to 3, is clearly more convenient.

The t-Student and the q-Gaussian functions are considered to form two different families by Nielsen and Okanura, 2022. "The Cauchy [Lorentzian] distributions belong to two larger families of distributions: Namely, the t-Student distributions (for $\nu=1$ degrees of freedom) and the q-normal distributions [Naudts] (for $q=2$). ... In information theory, the Cauchy distributions have been used to

model and analyze severe non-Gaussian noise with infinite variance ... modeling so-called Cauchy channels” (Nielsen & Okamura, 2022, and references therein). “Cauchy distributions are t-Student distributions with one degree of freedom and thus have heavier tails than Gaussian distributions which make them attractive for analyzing a variety of stochastic phenomena in source/channel coding and quantization” (Nielsen & Okamura mentioning Farvardin & Modestino).

In Wikipedia, we find $t\text{-Student} = C \left[1 + \frac{1}{v^2} t^2\right]^{-(v+1)/2}$, with $C = \frac{\Gamma((v+1)/2)}{\sqrt{v\pi}\Gamma(v/2)}$. It is also told that its characteristic function is ($v > 0$): $\frac{K_{v/2}(\sqrt{v}|t|) \cdot (\sqrt{v}|t|)^{v/2}}{\Gamma(v/2)2^{v/2-1}}$. The characteristic function is the Fourier transform of the probability distribution (calculation in Simon Hurst, 1985).

In Yin and Dong, 2023, we can find the “Bessel function expression of characteristic function”. The researchers are proposing a “unified method to derive the classical characteristic functions of all elliptical and related distributions in terms of Bessel functions”. They are presenting “the simple closed form of characteristic functions for commonly used distributions such as multivariate t , Pearson Type II, Pearson Type VII, Kotz type and Bessel distributions”, so we can enlarge the basin of functions which can be investigated by means of WolframAlpha. In fact, in Yin and Dong [arXiv](#), we can find the modified Bessel function of the second kind, with order v , defined by the following integral:

$$\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \int_0^\infty (1+w^2)^{-(v+1/2)} \cos(tw) dw = \frac{2^{1/2-v} |t|^v K_v(t \operatorname{sgn}(t))}{\Gamma(v + \frac{1}{2})}$$

This is the Fourier transform that we can obtain by means of WolframAlpha of function $(1+w^2)^{-(v+1/2)}$.

The expression of Pearson Type VII, is given in <https://www.originlab.com/doc/Origin-Help/PearsonVII-FitFunc> for instance, where it is told that the “peak function is a Lorentz function raised to a power”. In this case too we can use WolframAlpha to obtain its Fourier transform and therefore its time correlation function.

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